

PROJECT DELIVERABLE REPORT

Greening the economy in line with the sustainable development goals

D7.3.3 NAIADES Front-End and HMI Mechanisms and Integrated Decision Support Engine – User manual for Braila

A holistic water ecosystem for digitisation of urban water sector

SC5-11-2018

Digital solutions for water: linking the physical and digital world for water solutions

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Abbreviations

DSS	Decision Support System
HMI	Human Machine Interface
IP	Internet Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NN	Neural Network
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
UC	Use Case

1. Summary

This report provides the user manual for UC Braila, in order to be translated to Romanian for the convenience of the end-users, as well as the smooth adaptation of HMI to the Use Case.

The initial report was delivered in English and it was based on D7.3 HMI and integrated Decision Support System.

The final report was translated in Romanian by the UC leaders, in order to be delivered to the end-users.

2. Introduction

The scope of this deliverable is to provide an overall user manual about HMI, DSS and the other NAIADES components. This document will help the end-users to “unlock” the privileges of using the final platform in testing environments, such as the Use Cases.

D7.3 can be also used for the KPIs evaluation, as it will sustain an important pillar of learning for the end-users, and an actual proof of concept for the Project and its results.

2.1. Navigation into the Braila UC

2.1.1. Users and Roles

In Braila Use Case, there is one User created with one overall role. This user has an administrator role, meaning that he/she can see all the UC Braila Screens.

In order to log in, the end-user has to go to <http://naiades.simavi.ro/auth> and click on the “Connect to Keyrock” button.

*The above IP address will change when the HMI will be deployed in the final NAIDES server.

Figure 2.1-1 Connect to Keyrock

When the end-user clicks on the above button, then he/she is redirected to Keyrock main page.

Figure 2.1-2 Keyrock Sign In

The current user has the email address of braila-admin@gmail.com.

*The credentials will be not shared in this document, due to security measures.

Then, the end-user can click on the “Sign In” button and navigate into HMI’s Home Page.

Figure 2.1-3 Braila Homepage

2.1.2. Language Selection

The end-user clicks on the [drop-down](#) on the top-right menu. He can leave the predefined language, which is English as it is shown in the figure bellow. Or he/she can select Romanian, by clicking “RO” in the drop-down.

Figure 2.1-4 Romanian for Braila

After this, the end-user can navigate to the HMI to the language of his convenience.

2.1.3. User Management

There is also the option to create new users and roles. This capability is only applicable for the general administrator of Braila (like the user shared).

The administrator can select the configuration button on the top right, as the figure show below.

Figure 2.1-5 Configuration Button for User Management

When the user clicks on the button, then he redirects to the following page, and he has to confirm his credentials.

Figure 2.1-6 User Management Credentials

When the admin logs in, then he can show the already created users and their roles, like below.

Figure 2.1-7 User Management, Registered Users

The admin can change the roles from the already registered users by clicking on the role drop-down.

2.1.4. Water Demand

One of the most important screens of the HMI is the Water Demand Screen. This screen provides awareness coming from the installed water flow and pressure sensors in the Braila area.

Figure 2.1-8 Water Demand Screen

Functionality 1 - Water Flow & Pressure Sensors Map, DSS Alerts

Beginning from the first functionality, the end-user can detect the **locations** of the **Water flow** and **Pressure Sensors** on the **map**, as long as **set thresholds** on their measurements, in order to generate the **DSS alerts**.

Figure 2.1-9 Water Flow, Pressure Sensors, DSS alerts

In the above figure, the end-user can see the location of the water flow and pressure sensors. In order to easily detect their location, a memorandum is provided.

Moreover, the end-user can click on the “set thresholds”, in order to provide thresholds on the signals/measurements of the sensors themselves.

Set Thresholds ✕

WATER FLOW SENSORS ▾

SENSOR 318505H498 ▾

You can set new thresholds here.

Max Totalizer1

Min Totalizer1

Max Totalizer2

Min Totalizer2

Max Consumer Totalizer

Min Consumer Totalizer

Max Flow Rate

Min Flow Rate

Max Analog Input1

Figure 2.1-10 Set Thresholds on the Measurements of the Sensors

The end-user set the thresholds manually for the Water Flow and Pressure sensors and clicks on the [submit button](#).

Moreover, there is the capability to set thresholds for all pressure and flow sensors, by selecting the name of each sensor.

After this, if the incoming measurement from the sensors are over from any given threshold, the DSS generates an alert, as the following pictures demonstrates.

Pressure Sensors

16/11/2022 02:28
 Sensor 5770 value: 0 has been higher than normal maximum limit -1 for the last hour.

16/11/2022 02:28
 Sensor 5771 value: 18.7 has been higher than normal maximum limit -1 for the last hour.

16/11/2022 02:28
 Sensor 5772 value: 20.2 has been higher than normal maximum limit -1 for the last hour.

16/11/2022 02:28
 Sensor 5773 value: 0 has been higher than normal maximum limit -1 for the last hour.

Figure 2.1-11 DSS Alert on Water Flow and Pressure Sensors

The above figure informs the end-user that Totalizer1 from the Water Flow Sensors is above the limit. As a result, the end-user is aware that the Water Flow is in an abnormal state and an action must be provided.

Functionality 2 - Pressure and Water Flow Historical Data Graphs

The second functionality of this screen is focused on two historical graphs with input from the past water flow and pressure sensors.

In the first graph the end-user can see a graph with historical data from the pressure sensor 5772.

Figure 2.1-12 Pressure Historical Data Graph

figure. Pressure Historical Data Graph

The end-user can detect the “behaviour” of the incoming Pressure Sensor values (on the Y axis) alongside with the time when the data were received (on the X axis).

Moreover, there is a *drop-down* on the right with the aim of selecting different date than the one is shown. This drop-down provides the dates with given input.

Moreover, righter on the drop-down option, there is another drop-down, where the end-user can select the sensor by each id. The current version of the HMI has four different ids.

Also, if the end-user clicks on the memorandum with the sensor ids, then he can remove the sensors, in order to see only one, or a combination of them. He clicks again, in order to return all the sensors back in their default state.

The same functionality applies for the Water Demand Sensors, as it is shown in the following figure.

Figure 2.1-13 Water Flow Historical Graph

The end-user can detect the “behaviour” of the incoming water flow values (on the Y axis) alongside with the time when the data were received (on the X axis).

Again, the end-user can select another date for this sensor’s input and/or a different sensor.

Functionality 3 - Water Demand Prediction

This functionality provides the end-user with the awareness of a forecast for the water demand. More specifically, the Water Demand Prediction provides water consumption forecasts on the next hours of the day and next week, as the following diagram demonstrates.

Figure 2.1-14 Water Demand Prediction

Figure 2.1-15 Next Week Predictions

Another functionality that applies here is the total sum of all hourly or the weekly consumption, when the end-user selects the “total” option in the drop-down on the right.

Figure 2.1-16 Total sum of Next Hours Prediction

Figure 2.1-17 Total sum of Next Week Prediction

Functionality 4 - Modeled Flow Graph

This component uses hydraulic models to estimate the hourly pressure distributions of the upcoming 24h in the District Metered Area of Radu Negru in Braila, based on forecasts provided by the relevant service, and display corresponding maps.

Figure 2.1-18 Hydraulic models

The user clicks a ‘run’ button, in order to detect if the data is available to be gathered from the platform.

Then, the user selects the particular time (hour in the upcoming 24h), to display the corresponding map with the distribution of pressures from a drop-down on the top right.

The information provided in the maps is the following:

Figure 2.1-19 Final Map of Modeled Flow & Pressures from Forecast Demand

The end-user selects from the drop-down on the right the hours.

2.1.5. Weather Prediction

In the weather prediction screen, HMI provides a UI of weather prediction in Braila. More precisely, it provides:

- The current weather in Braila (Current Temperature, Humidity, Wind Speed and an overall.)
- DSS prediction of the weather per five hours for the following three days (e.g., Possible rain, clear weather, etc.)
- Predictions of the values for Temperature, Humidity and Wind Speed per 6 hours for the following three days
- Weather Historical data
- Weather Historical Graph

As a result, the end-user is enhanced with situation awareness, in order to take action if needed, mainly for the water consumption.

Figure 2.1-20 Braila's Weather Prediction screen

Figure 2.1-21 Weather Historical Data & Historical Graph

Functionality 1 - Braila Weather

Here, the end-user can detect the exact temperature, the humidity percentage and the wind speed of the Braila area.

Figure 2.1-22 Braila Weather

Functionality 2 - DSS Weather Prediction

Here, the end-user can see prediction on the weather for the next 3 days.

Figure 2.1-23 DSS Weather Prediction

These predictions/alerts are varied into “Possible rain”, “Clear weather”, “Warm Weather”, “Possible light rain” and “Dry Weather”.

Functionality 3 - Weather Forecast

The weather forecast provides to the end-user, details on the temperature, humidity and wind speed for the next 3 days.

Proгноза meteo

Zi/Ora (local)	20/05/2022 (10:00)	+6h (16:00)	+12h (22:00)	21/05/2022 (04:00)	+24h (10:00)	+30h (16:00)	+36h (22:00)	22/05/2022 (04:00)	+48h (10:00)	+54h (16:00)	+60h (22:00)	23/05/2022 (04:00)
Temperatura	10.2 °C	20.3 °C	16.8 °C	8.5 °C	10.5 °C	20.8 °C	17.3 °C	8.7 °C	10.8 °C	19.8 °C	15.6 °C	10.3 °C
Umiditate	83.3 %	37.5 %	45.1 %	75.8 %	79.8 %	33.8 %	35.4 %	82.8 %	85.1 %	41.0 %	47.9 %	72.7 %
Viteza vant	1.3km/h	2.1km/h	19km/h	0.9km/h	1.1km/h	2.6km/h	3.1km/h	1.4km/h	1.1km/h	2.4km/h	3.5km/h	1.8km/h

Figure 2.1-24 Weather Forecast

The end-user obtains a more complete picture on the upcoming weather and he/she can be prepared in case of unwanted difficulties.

Functionality 4 - Weather Historical data & Graph

The Weather historical table is filled with data from the past 3 days, as it is shown in the following figure.

Weather Historical

Day/Hour (Local)	02/06/2022 (10:00)	+6h (16:00)	+12h (22:00)	03/06/2022 (04:00)	+24h (10:00)	+30h (16:00)	+36h (22:00)	04/06/2022 (04:00)	+48h (10:00)	+54h (16:00)
Temperature	25.8 °C	24.4 °C	22 °C	21.3 °C	26.6 °C	25.5 °C	21.5 °C	18.1 °C	25.4 °C	27.5 °C
Humidity	62 %	69 %	83 %	87 %	61 %	69 %	84 %	70 %	64 %	45 %
Wind Speed	2 km/h	1.8 km/h	3.4 km/h	1.3 km/h	3.2 km/h	2.5 km/h	1.1 km/h	0.9 km/h	3.2 km/h	2 km/h

Figure 2.1-25 Weather Historical Data

These data are used in the historical graph, where the temperature, humidity and the wind speed can be shown from a popup if the end-user hovers on one of the 3 colored lines of the graph.

Weather Historical Graph 02/06/2022 - 05/06/2022

Figure 2.1-26 Weather Historical Graph

The green line refers to historical humidity, the blue to windspeed and the red one to temperature.

2.1.6. Water Treatment Lab

This screen provides to the end-user 2 nested sub-screens, the **Lab dWTP** and the **Braila dWTP**. These screens almost offer the same functionalities, with the difference that in the Braila dWTP the end user puts manually values of e.g., ph. measurement, instead to lab dWTP, where these values are integrated from the lab to the HMI.

Figure 2.1-27 Dynamic Treatment Suggestions

Lab dWTP

Functionality 1 - Historical Graph

This graph provides details on pH, Conductivity and Turbidity for a given time range. Moreover, if the end-users' hovers on the 3 lines of the graph, he/she can see a pop-up with the aforementioned values in a specific date.

Figure 2.1-28 Historical Graph on Inlet Measurements

Functionality 2- Suggested Treatments for specific date

If the end-user hovers on the historical graph, the suggested treatments will change on the right of the screen.

Figure 2.1-29 Suggested Treatments for historical data

These treatments are referring to coagulant and chlorine treatments that were suggested when the Platform received the values provided in the historical graph (in the previous chapter).

Moreover, the end-user can see the outlet values of turbidity and free chlorine, if the he selects the “outlet” option in the drop-down. The suggested treatments are provided too.

Figure 2.1-30 Historical Graph on Inlet Measurements

Functionality 3 - Last Measure Values

The last measured values are consumed every time the laboratory produces new values for pH, Conductivity and Turbidity.

Last Measured Values		17 Nov 2022 - 12:00
pH measurement		7.68556
Conductivity		0.045823 μ S
Turbidity		13.3213 NTU

Figure 2.1-31 Last Measured Values

This functionality provides a near real-time integration of the required values to the system. If new values are submitted, then the previous ones become historical values.

Functionality 4 - Last Suggested Treatments

This functionality refers to suggestions of the real-time values, the ones described in the previous chapter.

Last Suggested Treatments	
Treatment 1	Chlorination Dosage Recommendation: 26.463 g/m^3
Treatment 2	Coagulant Dosage Recommendation: 30.009999999999998 g/m^3

Figure 2.1-32 Last Suggested Treatments

These treatments refer to the chlorination and coagulant dosage recommendations.

Similarly, to the Last measured values, the last suggested treatments are integrated to the historical suggested treatments, when HMI receives new values.

Functionality 5 - DSS Feed

The Decision Support System is focused on the changes of the incoming values. More specifically, if any of pH, conductivity and turbidity has changed, then the DSS Produces an alert with the changed measurement.

DSS flux

Please check the suggested treatment. The following measurements have changed:
[conductivity]

Figure 2.1-33 DSS Feed Changed Values

DSS aware the end-user to check the suggested treatment if any of the values have been changed.

This functionality is based on given thresholds but also on the difference between the last measurement to the new one.

For instance, if conductivity value has changed and the difference of the last one to the new one is above 50, then a DSS alert is created.

The same approach applies with the turbidity (5 units difference) and pH (pH measurements must be between 6 and 8).

If the above values are produced and there is no change or conditional differences, then the DSS produces a simple message, that there is no change detected.

Measurements have no change

Figure 2.1-34 DSS Feed No Change

Braila dWTP

In the Braila dWTP screen, all functionalities are the same with the Lab dWTP, except one.

Functionality - Daily Values

The Daily Values are provided manually by the end-user, contrarily to the Lab dWTP, where these values are integrated to the HMI automatically.

Daily Values		03 Jun 2022 - 12:35	
pH masuratoare	<input type="text" value="7"/>	pH	
Conductivitate	<input type="text" value="124"/>	μS	
Turbiditate	<input type="text" value="90"/>	NTU	
<input type="button" value="Send Values"/>			

Figure 2.1-35 Daily Values in Braila dWTP

The end-users give values to the fields of the above form and clicks the “Send Values” button.

Then:

- The last suggested treatments generate the chlorination and coagulant dosage recommendations,
- The DSS Feed checks if the incoming data are in the required limit and if they are not create a warning
- After a while, the Daily Values become Historical data and they are visualized in the historical graph
- And the last suggested treatments become “suggested treatments for the time and date, the end-user provided the daily values.”

2.1.7. Water Observatory

The Water Observatory tool provided by JSI have the following functionalities.

- **Indicators:** adding to the global indicators we are ingesting curated open datasets that have regional information about water topics of interest to the stakeholder.
- **Media:** each location has its own news and social media streams configured to priorities and aspects of the news that stakeholders define as topics of interest (e.g., floods).
- **Research:** similarly, to the media sources, the research topics allow for some customization to better fit to the needs of the local user.
- **Resources:** the natural resources information provided for exploration is geolocated to the regions of interest to the user of the platform.

2.1.7.1. Indicators View

To better understand the evolution and correlation between aspects impacting water resources, and to better observe alignment with Sustainable Development Goals, the NAIADES Water Observatory provides the user with a set of dropdown menus where the user can choose the data sources in a three-

dimensional visualization. Here we consider a dynamic view over time on two axes and consider the size of balls to complete three dimensions of observation (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-36 Multidimensional animation in the analysis of global indicators

The local priorities of the NAIADES use cases are addressed in the “Local Indicator” tab changing from data ingested from global to local indicators. This view is showcasing the observation of water-related datasets linked to SDG 6 at world and country/region levels that can help us observe changes and trends (see Figure below). Both the local and global indicators can ingest new data sources that are identified of interest to, e.g., new added users bringing new priorities.

Figure 2.1-37 Higher granularity in the analysis of local indicators

To complement the analysis of indicators that can be sometimes unclear when the user wants to follow the progress of a single indicator, we have made available a single-indicator view, both to analyse global and local indicators in separate, when scrolling down from the animation, maintaining the selections. It is also possible to view the time-series deriving from the countries selected at each of these indicators in a single window for in-depth analysis (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-38 Analysis of a single indicator through time

An example of a workflow in the usage of this tab is to analyse the evolution of the water surface level, in comparison with the fresh surface water and the inland waters across 20 years in Spain, selecting the appropriate axis in the dropdown menu and changing the location from “All Countries” to “Spain”. The comparison with other countries is still visible but the behaviour for the case of Spain is highlighted. Then, to further analyse the “Alicante” case we select that case in the “Global” dropdown menu and have now available the “Local Indicators” tab. In this view, when focusing on the topic of the evolution of drinking water conditions in the past 20 years in Spain, we can compare, e.g., the volume of drinking water, to the apparent losses of drinking water and the aid to the volume of water supplied in the public network across Spanish regions.

Navigation into the platform, step by step. Please provide every functionality that the end-user can do.

2.1.7.2. Media View

Both the traditional news media and the social media are important sources of input to the analysis of best practices in similar scenarios, and the definition of early warnings for water events. This view is exploring the information from news and social media in the context of the exploration of water-related topics that include when the weather is favourable to floods and the historical information from news and published research on these weather-related events and how to better take decisions to solve them. The water-related news is sourced in real-time using powerful text mining methods based on Wikipedia concepts to collect about 1500 news articles per day across more than 60 languages, of which a part relates to water events around the world. When selecting the Use Case in the main menu on the left, the real-time stream of news is automatically configured to search for topics that relate to the priorities and interests of the stakeholders that helped define this view, thus addressing the local interests (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-39 Water-related news monitoring

The configuration of the news streams is done directly over the news engine API that is serving them but can be tested in the news monitoring part of the system. The user can choose water topics of interest and define priority levels, choose languages and categories, as well as define how rigorous this configuration must be, to model how much news articles the system is collecting (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-40 Comprehensive configuration of news sources

When the user aims to explore a certain water-related event, it can do so in the larger news engine EventRegistry. This will allow the user to further explore concepts related to the collected articles from a query, and the fundamental information that the news collection provides about the event. The user can explore the news through time and learn from what was published in the context of similar events in the region or other world regions where best practices can be derived and help planning for the future happenings (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-41 Historical news analysis at the external exploration dashboard

The system also allows the user to explore other topics that are related to the query formulated over news articles or events, to better understand how much are other topics (e.g., economy or education) associated with the water topic in analysis. At all times the subsample of news articles can be requested for further analysis (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-42 Water news categorification at the external exploration dashboard

The social media is also present through Facebook and Twitter with different data access characteristics, and applications. Through the news engine Event Registry, that we have access to in the context NAIADES supporting the research on the NWO, we are able to see the number of times that certain news is shared in Facebook and, thus, its impact in this online community.

On the other hand, we are also collecting the tweets related to certain water topics based on key-phrases in the original languages and locations of the NAIADES Use Cases. In the tab “Twitter Dashboard” we present several data visualisation modules and search boxes where the user can further configure the search to access, e.g., the average sentiment of the posts or the main topics over keywords (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-45 Analysis of news and twitter posts over an exploration tool

Finally, the version 2 of the NWO also makes available an exploratory tool to review a certain water-related topic and explore its subtopics. As shown in Figure above, the NAIADES user can query using key phrases (under “”) and use connectives to refine the search. Moreover, the user can drag the target over the automatically generated colorful clusters of subtopics to reprioritize the search results according to the defined objectives of this activity. The typical usage is the query on a certain topic using connectors AND, OR and Lucene-based language to search in the metadata. From the list of search results subtopics are generated and distributed into coloured clusters. The user will then drag the target over the subtopics that are more related to the aims of the study and with that movement the search results change position. The user can directly access the more relevant publications directly by clicking on their title.

2.1.7.3. Research View

The scientific research tab allows the user to explore the information provided by published science, and look in detail into the success stories that can be used in decision-making and water education at local level. While in the global view the user can compare the research on water topics across countries and years of publication (in the tab “top trends”), as well as the main trends on water-research and how they have changed along the past years. The user can change the scale to ease interpretation, or download the data and the chart itself (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-46 Identification of trends in the scientific research

Figure 2.1-47 Analysis of scientific research using an exploration dashboard

The user can also access the most recent research papers directly at this “Research” view on the “Recent papers” tab, where the details of each paper is exposed. For a further analysis, the user can access the external dashboard based on the text mining technology Searchpoint that allows to explore the literature by moving the pointer over clusters of subtopics related to the query topic and, by doing that, to reorder the articles that were queried. At the moment this is limited to the research articles in the MEDLINE open dataset that mostly relate to health topics, being relevant to explore water contamination topics.

An example of usage of this view follows that of the exploration of historical news data to access further details on a water-related event. The user can start to analyse the trends related to such event and how they evolve through time (e.g., fresh water resources), and then explore those selected trends directly in the published literature by using them as key-phrases.

2.1.7.4. Resources View

In this second version we added the dimension of natural resources to the exploration scenarios of the Water Observatory, based on ingested weather data from the ECMWF (on humidity, temperature and rainfall) and other open data sources, with a sophisticated engine to explore the states of that data and short/medium term predictions on aspects of that data. This new view will explore topics related to water in the context of the climate crisis, offering in the tab “Predictions” the long-term predictions for over 5 to 10 years on, e.g., the behaviour of a season in what regards humidity, rainfall or water levels, based on the collected historical data (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-48 Climate change visualisation over 10 years forecast on resources availability

Moreover, it will also allow the user (through the tab “Explore”) to explore the data based on the Markov chains visual representation technology Streamstory that can show in an interactive way the distinctions between states and how they interact. This complex data visualisation model can provide additional information at each node and each transition that can help the user explore the combination of factors that explain the dynamics of, e.g., the season in regards to natural resources.

Figure 2.1-49 Exploration of water resources through complex data visualisation

An example of usage of this view starts with the selection of topics that define the focus of the study (e.g., rainfall, humidity and water level) to analyse 5- and 10-years forecasts related to these. Then, the user will continue the analysis in the tab “Explore”, interacting with the data visualisation and exploring the relations between states, clicking on states and transitions to access their characteristics, and studying their impact in the context of the problem in analysis.

2.1.8. Leakages Braila

In Leakage Braila’s screen, HMI provides the UI of the leakage detection from the noise sensors in Braila, among other functionalities, such as add or exclude nodes.

Figure 2.1-50 Braila’s Leakage screen

Functionality 1 - Noise Sensors and Map

HMI provides the Noise Sensor Location to the Map with green pin.

Figure 2.1-51 Noise Sensors Location

The above pins illustrate the current location of the noise sensors, as well as measurements for each node, as the following figure shows.

Noise Sensors

Current locations

Noise sensor (5982): 7.0

Noise sensor (5981): 7.0

Noise sensor (2182): 15.0

Noise sensor (5980): 16.0

Figure 2.1-52 Noise Sensors' measurements

Functionality 2 - Suggest New Locations

If the end-user decides that the previous sensors must be moved, then he/she can click on the “[Send New Locations](#)” button.

Suggestions for new locations

Send New Locations

The process has started. Please wait for the new suggested locations

Figure 2.1-53 Send New Locations

This function has been established in order to provide new suggested locations for the already installed sensors, where there will not be any danger of leakage.

As it is shown in the figure above, a notification message is provided in order to aware the user that the process has started. This message will be removed, when HMI receive the suggestion from the dedicated AI service. This process can take part in a range of 1 day to 3 days.

Then, HMI consumes the new locations and integrate them to the map with blue pins.

Figure 2.1-54 New Suggested Locations

A pop-up is also created, in order to inform the end-user for the sensor id and if the sensor has to be moved. That means that the end-user can see on the map the Green Pin of the Noise sensor (5980), which is the current location of the sensor.

Figure 2.1-55 Pop-up for Noise Sensor Id

This alert is provided by DSS after a comparison of the current location of the noise sensor with the new suggested position.

After this, if the BRAILA partners move the noise sensors from the current position to the recommended, then the current location is deleted and the new suggested is taking its place. The blue returns to green, as it is show in the figure below.

Figure 2.1-56 Moved Sensor

This notification means that the sensor has been moved and the system updates it status as “moved”.

If the end-users move the sensors to a different location, then they can click again on the “Send New Locations” button, in order to generate new suggestions.

Last but not least, there is a red pin in the Leakages map, where the final leakage is detected.

Functionality 3 - Add/Exclude Nodes

HMI provides another capability of adding or excluding nodes in the map. This helps the end-user to have a more complete awareness on the leakages in the current area.

A second map has been integrated in to a drop-down, as the following figure demonstrates. The end-user clicks on the “Possible Locations” button, in order to navigate in the second map.

Figure 2.1-57 Map with all possible locations of Nodes

In the above map, there are 144 possible locations of nodes, integrated in the Braila Area. HMI brings the capability to add or exclude the above nodes, in order to better enhance the leakage detection.

In order to achieve this, a pop-up has been created with 2 options, “add” or “exclude”.

Figure 2.1-58 Pop-up for “add” or “exclude” a node from possible locations

If the end-user clicks on “Add” button, then the node with id 13 will turn from green to blue (the one in the instance of the above figure). That means the end-user accepts the possible location of this node, and he/she added to the map.

If the end-user clicks on “Exclude” button, then the node is excluded as a choice and the green pin turns to red.

If the end-user changes his/her mind for an addition or an exclusion of the node, there is the option to turn the Node’s state to its first site, by clicking “exclude” (if the node was added) or “add” (if the node was excluded).

Moreover, the pop-up on the figure below, provides the groups that a sensor is involved. Groups provide the user with the probability of leakage in these coordinates and they are divided to 0, 1, 2, 3. HMI provides an alert describing the group each time (alert field), meaning:

- Group 0 - High Possibility of Leakage
- Group 1 - Medium Possibility of Leakage
- Group 2 - Low Possibility of Leakage
- Group 3 - Very Low Possibility of Leakage

The groups are often updated by AI services and HMI automatically consumes the change, in order to update the end-user.

2.1.9. Cons. State Analysis

The consumption state Analysis tool provided by JSI is used for analysing the time series states.

The end-user can click on the dedicated option to the side menu, in order to see the HMI initial screen for this component.

Figure 2.1-59 Cons.State Analysis HMI Initial Screen

The end-user can see anomaly detection alerts for state analysis, as well as flow meta signal.

If a sensor does not provide any data, then HMI provides an alert, such as the last flow sensor in the above figure.

In addition, the end-user can receive more detailed information for the above, if he/she clicks on the button “Cons. State Analysis” on the down left of the screen.

Since the end-user is already log-in, he/she can see the main dashboard of this component.

In the main dashboard the models can be managed. On the “offline models” page private and public models are available. Private models can be shared at any time also with other users. By clicking on a model name user is presented with additional info (as dataset, user, creation time, type, is public, description).

Figure 2.1-60 Dashboard

Adding a new model is straightforward. In the first step the user clicks on a button named add. After that a page appears with an input field for uploading a dataset user wants to model. When file is successfully uploaded, the system renders a green message to notify the user about complete. User then proceeds to a new page, where enters all necessary configuration parameters in order to create a model. In the first step the user selects data attributes and then defines the time attribute. Next steps include fine tuning configurations, number of clusters and desired name of the model.

Figure 2.1-61 Page for uploading dataset

Figure 2.1-62 Model configuration 1

Figure 2.1-63 Model configuration 2

Page contains a Markov model on the top, attribute histograms describing specific state on the right side and tabs which additional information about each state (state history, coordinates, time, explanation tree) are placed on the bottom. Histograms on the right side and charts on the bottom are visible only after a user selects (clicks) one of the states.

Figure 2.1-64 Model page with rendered Markov chain

At the bottom of the Markov chain visualization, a slider is positioned. A user, by moving the slider, adjusts the minimal transition rates which are still shown on Markov chain visualisation.

At the beginning, user is presented with the most basic states (usually, two or three states). Another slider, available on the left, enables user to expand (or collapse) base states in a more complex states' structure. Besides using left slider, user can expand (or collapse) the states' structure with the mouse's scroll button.

Figure 2.1-65 Moving bottom slider for adjusting minimum probability

Figure 2.1-66 Changing scale with left slider or zoom switches between different scales in clustering

By selecting (clicking) a state, user can access state details, available through histograms on the right side or additional info at the bottom.

Histograms show state’s attributes’ distribution (blue part of histogram) and compares it to the overall attributes’ distribution (grey part of histogram). A similar information is available at the bottom, inside “Time” tab, where the distribution is available for three-time scales (hour of day, day of week, month).

Figure 2.1-67 Click on state, highlights state and outgoing links. It also renders histograms on right side of page and other charts in bottom tab menu.

Figure 2.1-68 Time tab in bottom menu includes histograms, which present distribution of time attribute in a dataset (hour of day, day of week, month).

In the (bottom) “Explanation tree” tab, a decision tree chart is available, providing information about how each of the states are named. Each tree node includes a pie chart, presenting proportion of a positive (green colour) and a negative (red colour) classified items.

Figure 2.1-69 Decision tree

External data sources can be added from tab named Data source in profile settings. Input form for addition of new data source is opened after clicking on add button on right side of screen, where user provides all necessary data needed to make online model work properly.

It is also possible to attach trigger events on each state. Events are added via form next to the Markov chain model. User needs to tick the checkbox, that state has an event, later is required to add an event id, which is used for notifications. After the event trigger is successfully added, a yellow label is shown at the top of the state.

Figure 2.1-70 Form for addition of new data source

Figure 2.1-71 Adding event trigger to the state

The models can be integrated in an external, custom apps / websites. For this purpose, we have developed a first version of JavaScript library which renders preselected models in any external user app / website according to export configuration. Export configuration determines which components are rendered and how the external apps / websites interact with the states analysis tool. A user, in order to render any model on an external app / website, is required to provide API tokens. Tokens are generated in profile settings page with a click on button generate, which creates unique sequence of different symbols. Currently, not particularly relevant to T4.4, a new functionality, enabling restriction of tokens to a specific domain, (e.g., naides.ijs.si) are being added. Users can access only their own tokens and are able to edit or remove tokens.

Figure 2.1-72 Generate new API token

Figure 2.1-73 List of API tokens

3. Conclusions

By following the above navigation approach, the end-user will be enhanced with situation awareness for the leakage detection, water demand, among other functionalities. This knowledge will enable an accurate, real-time and worthy way of facing unwanted incidents, as water waste.

